

Interdisciplinary and Collaborative Research as a Panacea for Sustainable Development in Taraba State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research work investigated the effectiveness of interdisciplinary and collaborative research in attaining sustainable development in Taraba state, Nigeria. Hinged on the systems and social constructivism theories, the study used simple random sampling technique and 385 sample size drawn from seven (7) government tertiary institutions in the state- Taraba State University Jalingo, Federal University Wukari, College of Education Zing, College of Agriculture Jalingo, College of Health Technology Takum, Taraba State Polytechnic Jalingo and Federal Polytechnic, Bali. Findings revealed that, although, interdisciplinary collaborative research in Nigeria plays a crucial role in actualising Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) due to its accompanying benefits, such researches are to some extent lacking in Taraba state due to numerous challenges. The study, however, recommends that since effective interdisciplinary collaborative partnerships combines many disciplines/methods to curb difficult developmental issues, encouraging and cultivating collaborative culture between and among researchers/disciplines and strategic funds provision and allocation for interdisciplinary collaborative research becomes necessary.

Keywords: Collaborative, Interdisciplinary Research, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Introduction

The 21st century introduces unprecedented challenges to the world, including issues like environmental degradation, poverty, inequality and climate change (Ono, Iida & Yamazaki, 2017). Beyond the conventional borders of academic fields, an interdisciplinary approach is needed to address these difficulties. In order to handle these complex difficulties and achieve sustainable development, interdisciplinary and collaborative research has emerged as the remedy (Omisore, Babarinde, Bakare &